

THE NATURE OF SYNONYMY AS A BASIC UNIT OF LANGUAGE VOCABULARY.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8012840>

Tilavova Malika Mamaraimovna

Teacher of English

Language Theory and Practice Department,

Djizak State Pedagogical University

Annotation.

In this article, synonyms are one of the tools that show the wide possibilities and lexical richness of the language, and its place in the language world is widely covered based on the research of scientists and examples. Synonymy is considered one of the factors that cause disproportion between form and content, and it applies to all levels of language units larger than phonemes. Also, in the article, the meaning of lexical units is considered a central issue in the explanation of synonymy and, as observed in other phenomena of the language, linguistic units borrowed from other languages make a great contribution in turning the synonymy of lexical units into a unique system.

Key words.

synonym, ideographic, denotational, stylistic synonyms, connotational, components, absolute synonyms, phraseological synonyms, lexical synonymy, stylistic synonyms, textual synonyms.

A very important principle of grouping words in a language is the synonymic principle according to similarity (sameness) of meaning. **A synonym** (Greek *same + name*) is a word that has the same or nearly the same meaning as another word. Fast and quick are synonyms. We can say *a hard task* or *a difficult task*, because hard and difficult are synonyms. Synonymous words are one of the tools that show the wide range of opportunities and lexical richness of the language. Such words, which have different forms and express the same concept at different levels, are important tools that provide textual color.

Synonyms are words that may be interchanged in some contexts. It is often said that there are very few pairs of words in English that are entirely interchangeable, because there are usually slight but important differences between synonyms. Sometimes one synonym is more learned than another: *edifice* is more learned and pretentious than *building*. Sometimes one of a pair of synonyms is

informal: *smidgeon* is less formal than *particle*. Often learned words are rather specific in their suggestions; the sphere in which they can be used is narrow. It is possible to analyze both *terrestrial* and *mundane* as "pertaining to the world." But *terrestrial* is likely to suggest contrast between our world and other heavenly bodies, described by words like *lunar* and *solar*, and *mundane* carries with it suggestions of the practical, routine, everyday affairs of this world, as contrasted with more spiritual matters. Synonyms may differ, too, in expressing value judgments: to be *resolute* is a virtue; to be *determined* expresses no value judgment; and to be *obstinate* is a fault.

Synonymy is considered one of the factors that cause the disproportion of form and content, and it applies to all level units of the language larger than the phoneme. In the coverage of synonymy, the meaning of lexical units is a central issue. As observed in other phenomena of the language, linguistic units borrowed from other languages have a significant contribution to the transformation of the synonymy of lexical units into a unique system.

English is very rich in synonyms. There are about 8,000 synonymic groups in English. "Having thrown its doors wide open to Latin and Romance loan words English has greatly enriched its synonymic resources, obtaining delicate shades of meaning and ensuring variety on a scale no other European language can equal (e.g.: *deep* - *profound*, *begin* - *commence*, *dead* - *action*, *ask* - *question*, *interrogate*.)" (St. Ullmann. Semantics. Oxford, 1962.)

English is rich in synonyms for the historical reason; its vocabulary has come from two different sources, from Anglo-Saxon on one hand and from French, Latin and Greek on the other. Word borrowing, word derivation, semantic change, and other processes keep going on all the time, making English rich in synonyms.

Since English is considered to be a Germanic language from a historical point of view, the Anglo-Saxon words are often considered to be "native while those borrowed from other languages are "foreign". The native words are often shorter and less learned, for example: *buy* and *purchase*, *world* and *universe*, *teaching*, *guidance* and *instruction*. A characteristic pattern of English synonymic sets is the pattern including the native and the borrowed word: *begin* (Native; neutral) - *commence* (French, between bookish and colloquial) - *initiate* (Latin, bookish). The peculiar feature of English is the contrast between stylistically neutral native words, literary words borrowed from French and learned words of Latin and Greek origin: *division* - *part* - *branch*; *rise* - *mount* - *ascend*; *kingly* - *royal* - *regal*.

Each synonymic group comprises the most general word in a given group of synonyms. For example: in the group of verbs *to hope*, *to anticipate*, *to expect*, *to*

hope is the most general word that stands for any Of these words; it is called the **synonymic dominant**. Consider the following sets: *work, toil, drudgery, labour, grind, job, task; famous, celebrated, distinguished, eminent; fashionable, chic, dressy, elegant, modish, smart, stylish, trendy.*

A synonymic dominant is the most general word in a given group of synonyms, a word belonging to the basic stock of words, stylistically neutral, having high frequency of usage, vast combinability, lacking connotations. It expresses the notion common to all the members of the group in the most general way without any additional information.

Synonyms are subdivided into different groups:

1. **Ideographic** or denotational: the difference in the meaning concerns the notion expressed: *change - alter - vary; understand - realize; to walk - to pace - to stroll - to stride.*

2. **Stylistic** synonyms have the same denotational components but differ in connotational components of meaning: *hearty-cordial; imitate-monkey; terrible-horrible-atrocious.* Among stylistic synonyms we find archaic/modern (*oft - often*); neologisms/common (*baby-moon - artificial satellite*); British/American (*post - mail*); euphemisms (*die - pass away*).

Very often we cannot draw a strict line of demarcation between ideographic and stylistic synonyms, as they are interwoven. Difference of the connotational component is accompanied by some variation of the denotational meaning of synonyms, that is why it would be more consistent to subdivide synonymous words into ideographic, stylistic and ideographic-stylistic synonyms, for example: *intelligent - shrewd - clever - bright - sagacious; to continue - to endure - to last - to persist.*

English scholars speak also of **absolute synonyms** of exactly the same meaning (*ash - ravan*) and of **phraseological synonyms** which are used in different collocations: *language - tongue (only mother tongue); cardinal - main (only 4 cardinal points).* There are also contextual synonyms that are similar in meaning under some specific distributional conditions (e.g. *get* and *buy*).

Many synonyms in the English language reflect the history of the formation of the English vocabulary (*hand - part - share; hand - handwriting*). Contraction creates synonyms (*comfortable - comfy*). The sources of synonymy are borrowing, abbreviation, desynonymization and, in modern times, the formation of phrasal verbs (*to turn down - to reject, to call off - to cancel, to give up - to abandon*).

Synonymous relations in the language exist not only between lexical units, but also between pronunciation variants of phonemes, stable combinations,

morphological devices and syntactic devices. General rules and requirements for synonymy apply to all of them and apply to all of them.

L. G. Barlas explains the differences between different forms of synonyms, i.e., *lexical synonymy* and *phraseological synonymy*, as follows: variantness is the same, synonymy is a characteristic of different language units. Variants mean different forms of the same language unit that differ slightly in form. There should be no differences in lexical and grammatical meanings because they form one word, one word form or construction. Synonyms are different words, forms of words, devices whose meanings are close to each other.

The classification of synonyms has been the focus of its researchers. Based on the existence of this phenomenon in language layers, Sh. Rakhmatullayev initially divides them into lexical and grammatical synonymy. In turn, dictionary synonymy is divided into lexical, phraseological and lexical-phraseological types. According to the difference in meaning, it lists their types, such as semantic synonyms (ideographic synonyms), stylistic synonyms, and speech synonyms. Among such classifications, which facilitate the study and understanding of synonyms, I. B. Golub's classification deserves attention. According to him, synonyms that differ in shades of meaning are semantic synonyms, and synonyms that have the same meaning are called stylistic synonyms. Stylistic synonyms include synonyms that refer to different task styles and belong to one task style and differ in different emotional-expressive shades. Synonyms that differ both in meaning and stylistic color are considered semantic-stylistic synonyms. About the classification of synonyms, Z. I. Khovanskaya writes the following: "Lexical synonyms - belonging to the same word family, retaining signs of gender and type in their meaning, related to the same level of abstraction and denotative or a language unit that differs in stylistic components of meaning".

It is extremely important for methodological research that synonymous relations exist not only in the language system, but also appear in the text created at the expense of units of all language levels, which participate in the methodological branching of language units and perform methodological tasks in the process of communication. Such synonyms are called textual synonyms.

In conclusion, it can be said that the writer's language skills are also observed in his use of lexical semantics. It is obvious that synonyms are used to ensure image clarity, artistic perfection, and emphasis on the main idea. The wealth of synonyms in English gives us a variety of ways of expressing ourselves, but challenges us to decide on the most appropriate of them.

REFERENCES:

1. Tilavova, M. (2021). The Impact Of Motivation In Learning Foreign Languages. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 4(9).
2. Галина Бабич: Lexicology: A Current Guide. Лексикология английского языка. Учебное пособие Flinta.2022
3. Tilavova, M. M. (2022). THEORETICAL GRAMMAR OF ENGLISH AND THE MAIN DOMAINS OF LANGUAGE IN IT. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2022(1), 320-330.
4. Tilavova, M. (2021). РОЛЬ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ В ЖИЗНИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 4(9).
5. Tilavova, M. (2021). Variability Of Phraseological Units In English And Semantic Problems In Translation. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 4(9).
6. Tilavova, M. (2021). The importance of learning a second language and its benefits for the individual. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 4(9).
7. Tilavova, M. (2021). INVERSION IS A BRIDGE TO THE WONDERS OF THE LANGUAGE WORLD. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 2(3).
8. Mamaraimovna, T. M. (2022, January). THE ROLE OF MODERN UZBEK WOMEN IN THE PROSPERITY OF THE MOTHERLAND. In Conference Zone (pp. 226-230).
9. Saporbayevich, A. O., & Mamaraimovna, T. M. (2022). THE STRUCTURAL FEATURES OF WORDS RELATED TO EDUCATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(14), 123-128.
10. Saporbayevich, A. O., & Mamaraimovna, T. M. (2022). Using educational idioms in English and they are a bright way to get to know the lives of native speakers. NAMANGAN INSTITUTE OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY, 17-20
11. Tilavova, M. (2021). THE USE OF THE INVERSION IN THE LITERARY CONTEXT. *Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation*, 32(3), 35460-35471.
12. Tilavova, M. M. (2022). EFFECTIVENESS OF STATE YOUTH POLICY IN OUR COUNTRY. *Mental Enlightenment Scientific-Methodological Journal*, 2022(1), 277-286.
13. Tilavova, M. M. (2022). NATURE OF SEMANTIC CHANGE: LINGUISTIC METAPHOR AND LINGUISTIC METONYMY. *INTERNATIONAL*

SCIENTIFIC-PRACTICAL CONFERENCE THE 3RD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON XXI CENTURY SKILLS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING, 131-133.

14. Tilavova, M. M. (2022). LEXICOGRAPHY IS AS A BASIS OF LINGUISTIC INTERPRETATION. INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC-PRACTICAL CONFERENCE THE 3RD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON XXI CENTURY SKILLS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING, 153-155.

15. Tilavova, M. (2021). Innovative Technologies Are the Demand of the Modern Era and the Path to the Door of Success. International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development, 6(1), 1410-1412.

16. Tilavova, M. (2020). The Power Of The Mysterious Inversion In Literary Books. THE AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE AND EDUCATION INNOVATIONS, 2(11) 592-598.

17. Tilavova, M. (2020). TIL- DUNYO MO'JIZALARINI O'RGANISHGA ELTUVCHI KO'PRIK. НАУКА И ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ВЫСОБЫ XXI ВЕКА, 11(4), 71-75.

18. Ахмедов, О., & Тилавова, М. (2023). SEMANTIC STRUCTURE OF WORDS RELATED TO EDUCATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Scienceproblems. uz, 3(1), 51-62.

19. Малика, Т. М. (2023). ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИЕ ЕДИНИЦЫ, СВЯЗАННЫЕ С ОБРАЗОВАНИЕМ, КАК ВАЖНЫЕ И НЕОБХОДИМЫЕ ТЕРМИНЫ. SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 1(12), 196-203.

20. Tilavova, M. (2023). POLYSEMY IN LINGUISTICS AS A MULTIFACETED AND COMPLEX PHENOMENON. Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики, 6(1).

21. Tilavova, M. (2023). TEACHING SEMANTICS TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS: This article provides information about how English language learners can be taught semantics and their types. Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики, 6(1).

22. Saporbayevich, A. O., Mamaraimovna, T. M., & Abdug'appon o'g'li, A. N. (2022). THE USE OF LEXICAL UNITS RELATED TO EDUCATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. JOURNAL OF NORTHEASTERN UNIVERSITY, 25(04), 1383-1397.

23. Xayriniso, U. (2023). OPPORTUNITIES OF INTERNET IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE CLASSROOM. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 11(2), 650-652.

24. Sevinch, A., & Xayriniso, U. (2023). FRAZEOLOGIK LUG 'ATLAR HAQIDA UMUMIY MA'LUMOTLAR. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(8), 304-307.

25. Uzoqova, X. (2023). THE USE OF SMARTPHONES AND APPS TO IMPROVE ENGLISH LEARNERS'SKILLS IN THE CLASSROOM. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(5), 365-371.

26. Saporbayevich, A. O., & Mamaraimovna, T. M. (2023). SEMASIOLOGY IS THE WORLD OF MEANING OF WORDS AND PHRASES. MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH, 2(19), 73-77.

27. Малика, Т. М. (2023). ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИЕ ЕДИНИЦЫ, СВЯЗАННЫЕ С ОБРАЗОВАНИЕМ, КАК ВАЖНЫЕ И НЕОБХОДИМЫЕ ТЕРМИНЫ. *SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 1(12), 196-203.

28. Tilavova, M. (2023). POLYSEMY IN LINGUISTICS AS A MULTIFACETED AND COMPLEX PHENOMENON. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 6(1).

29. Tilavova, M. (2023). TEACHING SEMANTICS TO ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNERS: This article provides information about how English language learners can be taught semantics and their types. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 6(1).

30. Малика, Т. М. (2023). ЛЕКСИЧЕСКИЕ ЕДИНИЦЫ, СВЯЗАННЫЕ С ОБРАЗОВАНИЕМ, КАК ВАЖНЫЕ И НЕОБХОДИМЫЕ ТЕРМИНЫ. *SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 1(12), 196-203.

31. Tilavova, M. (2023). STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC CHARACTERIZATION OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TERMINOLOGY IN THE SPHERE OF EDUCATION. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 6(2).

32. Малика, Т. М. (2023). NEOLOGISM WORDS AS ONE OF THE MAIN TOOLS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING. *INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION*, 2(18), 88-93.

33. Малика, Т. М. (2023). PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS ARE A WEALTH OF VOCABULARY THAT ENRICHES THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 3 (30), 173-178.